

**THE ASSESSMENT ON THE APPLICATION OF SCHOOL
ADMINISTRATOR SELECTION IN TURKEY RELATED TO
COMPETENCY AND CAREER PRINCIPLES OF
HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT**

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Abstract:

Administrators are the most responsible people for achieving goals of educational institution. That administration fulfills schools' aims effectively and efficiently depends on whether administrative functions are carried out according to scientific principles. The aim of the study was the assessment on school administrators' selection done as part of the last regulation, published on 10th June 2014 and related to administrators' assignments of educational institutions depended on National Education Ministry according to expediency of competency and career which are principles of human resources management. The data, collected from nineteen school administrators, vice-principals and teachers who participated in the oral the exam conducted as part of this regulation with a semi-structure interview form, were analyzed with the help of content analyses method. As a result, most of the participants stated that it wasn't acted appropriately enough for the principles of competency and career principles except for access to the exam. Field experts should select school administrators by taking into consideration principles of human resources management.

Keywords: competency, career, school administrator

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1. Introduction

Organizations can fulfill both their own aims and individual aims by using different skills, knowledge and power of personnel in their own structures (Aydın, 2010). It was thought whether the properties people had was managed efficiently or badly affected on the value of human resources in the organizations (Owens and Valley, 2004). Reaching organizational aims is related to meeting needs of personnel and human resources management includes needs of the personnel (Fındıkçı, 1999). Mahapatro (2010) defined the human resources management as a process brought together aims of personnel with aims of organization. Furthermore, human resource management is an art which provides qualified labor forces, improves and maintains them.

Selection and recruitment of personnel is one of the nine functions of human resources management accepted by Association for Talent Development (ASTD). One aim of the human resources management is providing that personnel are employed by using *“their skills and abilities in the most effective and efficient manner”* (zgen & Yalçın, 2010). Recruitment is a process which complies people and their needs with properties of work and career opportunities in the organization (Mahapatro, 2010). Byars and Rue (2008) defined recruitment as looking for qualified personnel among lots of people for vacancies and it is a process attracting them to the organization. Furthermore, they emphasized that recruitment of appropriate personnel was the most important priority when this process aimed continuity of the organization effectively and efficiently.

Recruitment is thought as one crucial of the process for organization. There are some important elements of recruitment: recruitment process of an organization in the past, making efforts to provide that personnel continue their works, working conditions, salary and advantages provided by organization and work will affect personnel which are working now and will work in the future. Moreover, what people think about the organization, attraction of the work, domestic policies of the organization and effect of the government impress the work applications. Correspondingly, the varieties in personnel pool of the organization as well as the possibility of recruitment of the most talented personnel for a work are affected (Decenzo & Robbins, 2002). Generally, recruitment proceedings in an organization are carried out by human resources management department (Byars & Rue, 2008). There are some fundamental principles of human resources management whose aim is to provide personnel recruitment effectively and efficiently. This area can be interpreted through these principles although they sometimes may change from one society to the others by means of experiences (Can, Akgn & Kavuncubaşı, 2001). Organizations can be successful if only they use these principles as a guide (Tunçer, 2011).

“Increasing attention has been directed in recent years to competencies in the workplace- both to the definition of the term competencies and to their use in testing, selection and training.”

(Russ, 1995:329)

One of these principles is competency. Competency is a main skill, potential power or motivation and it can be showed through behaviors observed in the different ways. It exists as knowledge, skill, behavior, motivation and characteristics in different part of personality (Mahapatro, 2010). Tyson (2006) also used the term to explain necessary properties for effective working. According to him, competency is a mixture of characteristics and properties of the work or it is only an adjective related to them. Yüksel (2000) divided the competency term into two parts according to its narrow and broad sense in this context. In the strict sense, competency means announcing the exam suitably to select the most appropriate person and doing the exam which can evaluate knowledge and skills required for the work. And in the broad sense, it is to provide employing effective and efficient employees. For organizational effectiveness, those expected from school administrators was named as competencies of school administrators. Some researches were done about competencies of school administrators. Duty and responsibilities, different characteristics, leadership styles in different area and communication skills of them can be thought among these researches. (Ağaoğlu, E., Altinkurt, Y., Yılmaz, K., &Karaköse, 2012). Furthermore, Tortop (1999) summarized competency principles as follows: 1) Announcing vacancies to those concerned; 2) Wanted properties should be reasonable and be related to the work; 3) Giving opportunity to apply everybody who has wanted properties; 4) A method which enables to enumerate the candidates to their competencies and skills, should be used and 5) Announcing the results and giving rights to object (p.48).

The other principles are career. According to Roe (1999), career is defined in two ways. The first of them is the position a personnel is working at and the other is to be promoted to a higher position (Çetin, 1999). The second meaning of career is more appropriate than the first one. According to 657 numbered State Personnel Law, career is defined as *“State Personnel were provided opportunities for promotion to the highest position in his\her class in accordance with necessary knowledge for their service and education conditions”*. Can, Akgün and Kavuncubaşı (2001) explained this principle as promotion in duty. This promotion enables a personnel gain more money, power and take more responsibility. In career system, a) Becoming expert in a specific work branch is taken into consideration. b) The promotion and success of a personnel is main principle. c) Interconnected labor and service groups are based on. d) The statement of the personnel

is determined according to status and laws. e) It is concentrated on before service and in-service education to provide for becoming expertness. f) Seniority and term of employment were considered g) Competency principle is taken into consideration is a condition to improve career system. h) A salary system parallel with steady advancing and promotion is carried out (Tortop, 1999:93).

Aydın (2013) stated that human resources should be designed logically. Moreover; competency, career and loyalty should be adopted as main principles in the administration science. It is important to determine the competencies of school administrators in a manner accepted by everybody, validly and faithfully as well as considering needs for an effective education system (Ağaaolu et al, 2012). In developed countries, such as ABD, Japan and Great Britain, graduate education on management and the management certificate were required (Akın, 2012). This situation might be thought competency on management was considered important in these countries. Furthermore; in Germany, one of the important criteria is competency while being selected as a school administrator though there are some differences among its states (Sng, 2012). As for career, if the managers were provided for opportunities related to their career development, they wouldn't be interested in the other organizations (Peterson, 2009). Moreover, according to Paul and Anantharaman (2004) career development and friendly work environment have positive relationship with organization commitment of the personnel.

The applications on selection and recruitment of school administrators in Turkey are being conducted in accordance with the regulation published on 10th June 2014. This application has two main properties. First, one is school administrators are assigned for four years (temporarily) rather than permanently. And the second one is that it designs extension of duty term whose school administrators are still serving and have expired their four years besides procedures of first assignments of them.

This study is important from the point of evaluating the applications on selection and recruitment of school administrators in Turkey regard to principles of human resources management. In addition to this, it provides suggestions for improvement on the basis of scientific data. For this purpose, it was sought answers to following questions through the views whose candidates participated in oral exam process done for assignment:

1. What are the views of school administrator candidates on the appropriateness of the selection and assignment procedure of formal school administrator to competency principle?

2. What are the views of school administrator candidates on the appropriateness of the selection and assignment procedure of formal school administrator to career principle?

2. Method

This study aimed to put forward the views and experiences of school administrator candidates on the selection and assignment procedure of formal school administrator in Turkey regard to principles of human resources management deeply. Information on social fact can be obtained profoundly by coming into natural worlds of people in qualitative researches (Mayring, 2000). Moreover, the qualitative research method focuses on process, understanding and meanings and uses inductive aspect besides comprehensive descriptions (Merriam, 2014). Thus, the use of qualitative research method in this study was thought more appropriate.

2.1 The Research Model

Phenomenology model which is one of the qualitative research models was used in this study. According to Merriam (2014) in phenomenology studies, it is aimed the understanding of structure and main items of the fact investigated through views whose people experienced it. The data were collected via semi-structure interview forms in this study. Firstly, main questions on the research topic were determined. Then through probe questions, deep meanings in the views of the participants were tried to reveal.

2.2 Sampling

In this study, maximum variation sampling of purposeful sampling was used. The aim of the method isn't to generalize, but it is to determine whether there is the common or shared phenomenon or not and to find different parts of the problem. Thus, the data and results which will be found through this method can be more fruitful than data and results arisen through the other methods (Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2013). "*Data sources of the [phenomenological](#) study are people or group of people who experience and can reflect on or express this phenomenon.*" (Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2013:80). So, nineteen participants who took part in the application of school administrators' assignment which was conducted in accordance with regulation published in June of 2014 were interviewed for this study. Participants were chosen among people who were working as teachers, vice principals or school administrators at that time. Some participants won the exam and

became school administrators or their duty terms have been prolonged. The others have gotten back to teaching.

2.3 Analyses

Data analyses aimed at explaining researched phenomenon through experiences and its meanings. The phenomenon is tried to explain with the help of descriptive expression of theme and direct citations (Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2013). The data collected through a semi structure interview form were analyzed under question titles in the form. The views of every participant examined separately and then they were examined comparatively. By including direct citations, it was tried to prosper the expressions.

Two researches took part in the first interview together to reach agreement for coding data among them. The research processes were written in detailed and by keeping the data, it was provided opportunity for controlling and reconsideration. The research questions were shared with participants and it was understood that their experiences coincided with the result of this study. Then it was obtained confirmations of participants. By selecting participants from all groups taking part in the exam, the variety of study group was provided.

3. Findings

The questions about the regulation related to Assignments of Educational Institutions' Administrators dependent on National Education of Ministry published on 10th June of 2014 were asked to the participants. It was asked for that participants evaluated this application by relating with competency and career of human resources management. The findings were presented in accordance with the order of the questions in the interview form.

1. The views of the school administrator candidates on the application of this regulation were evaluated under six different aspects. The assessment of the participants on whether:

- a) All candidates could be access to the exam related to administrators selection process
- b) The most competent the administrators were selected as a result of administrators selection process
- c) The conditions related to selections of administrators were realistic
- d) Candidates were put into the appropriate order as a result of administrator's selection process

e) Anything was taken into consideration except for the candidates' skills during the selection process.

1a. The Assessment Of The Participants On Whether Candidates Could Be Access To The Exam Related To Administrator Selection Process.

Eighteen participants stated that there wasn't any problem about accessibility to the exam. The exam announced through several ways. Only one participant had a hesitation about it. The participant thought that exam announcement was made but it wasn't clear whether everybody was aware of. The views of participants who thought announcement of the exam was made in a way to ensure that all candidates were informed were given down:

"There weren't any problems on announcement of the exam. Everybody was aware of the exam because the communication instruments are things which everybody can read and hear." (P5)

"The application duration was taken short but exam was announced by signature. Everyone who desired participated in the exam. Accessibility to the exam was provided through written and electronic communication instruments" (P12).

The opinion of the participant who wasn't clear about this topic was presented below:

"The exam was announced through internet and technological devices. I don't know how many people were aware of and participated in the exam. It wasn't explained." (P9)

1b. The Assessment Of The Participants On Whether The Most Competent Administrators Were Selected As A Result Of Administrator Selection Process.

While eighteen participants believed that the most competent administrators weren't selected, only one participant thought they were chosen as a result of administrator selection process. The view of the participant who thought that that the most competent administrators were selected indicated below:

"Yes, I think so. The regulation can meet the demand on the face of it. But I don't know how the implementers applied it. I think we can see problems in the progress of time." (P1)

There were some views of participants who believed the most competent administrators weren't selected as the result of this process owing to some reasons. And the reasons whose participants stated were grouped into two categories, arising from the regulation and the reason resulting from its application.

It was understood that, there were problems on the application of the exam process predominantly according to the views of participants who thought the most competent people weren't selected in the result of the exam (13 candidates stated). And there were some direct citations about it.

"Managerial experience is very important to be school administrator in my opinion. However, most of accomplished school administrators I know were considered unsuccessful in the oral exam. I think to be considered them as unsuccessful is loses for our education system. Long profession experience was ignored." (P7).

"I don't think the competent people weren't selected. The people who are good at memorizing or lucky, that is the people could choose the question they knew from out of 1500 questions besides being cheerful and not being exciting, were selected." (P12).

Moreover, there were opinions of people who thought that because of the reasons arising from the regulation the most competent people weren't selected. The direct citation about it as follows:

"It wasn't right to select administrators through an oral exam and thought them as competent. I think there must be something related to this application. There is some inadequacy." (P15).

"There isn't objectivity, clearness, consistency in the exam. It is inadequate and unreliable exam. I think it isn't an exam, but a selection organization." (P19).

1c. The Assessment Of The Participants On Whether The Conditions Related To Selections Of Administrators Were Realistic.

There were different ideas on this topic. Nine participants thought that the conditions related to selections of administrators weren't realistic while one participant believed they were realistic. Two participants stated some conditions were realistic but some weren't. Seven participants thought that there wasn't any problem about conditions but about application process of the exam. The views of participants who

thought that the conditions related to selections of administrators were unrealistic were given below:

“Actually, the questions hadn’t quality which can evaluate management skills. The duties related to official documents are being done with school personnel and vice principals as well as civil servants. But these kinds of duties aren’t only representative for a school. A school administrator should have communication skills and leadership characteristic to lead his\her school. S\he should have mission and vision. When we take into consideration these properties, the exam questions are too simple.” (P8).

“The conditions are inadequate. The person who has worked as a teacher for eight years can’t be a school administrators. In my opinion, an administrator candidate should be working as an administrator. If a person who hasn’t worked as an administrator was assigned, problems would be experienced.” (P16).

“We can see that the conditions related to selection of administrators are abstract and doesn’t meet the needs because there is exam phenomenon everywhere in Turkey and our thinking systems are affected by the exams.” (P1).

The views of participants who thought that the conditions related to selections of administrators were realistic were given below:

“It is accurate. Especially, if we removed appendix 2 and the points of being a teacher was higher, appendix 1 would be more accurate. But the conditions were realistic.” (P2).

The other statements were given below:

“We can say that when I looked at the questions, they could be realistic. The only issue is being objective. If we try to use politic way or other things, there will problems. The best thing is being objective.” (P4).

“I believed that it was true as structural. If it was done objectively and justly, it would be suitable for administration selection method. But I believed that the application of this wasn’t so.” (P18).

1d. The Assessment Of The Participants On Whether Candidates Were Put Into The Appropriate Order As A Result Of Administrator Selection Process.

Fifteen participants thought that the candidates weren't put into appropriate order. However, two participants stated that sequencing of candidates was accurate and two participants had hesitation. That is, they weren't sure whether the candidates put in order respectively the most successful, moderately successful and unsuccessful or not. The views of participants who considered to be done inappropriate order were given below:

"I know successful school administrators from public opinion, newspapers and during my managerial duty process. And these people were eliminated by being showed unsuccessful. The duty durations of people seeming as unsuccessful were prolonged but I don't know their relationships with students, parents and environment Successful school administrators were inhibited."(P5). "I don't think appropriate order was done because the participants were evaluated based on oral responses and the answers given at that time. Moreover; I think the assessment dependent on perception of evaluator can change from a person to a person." (P6).

The opinions in favor of being made appropriate order were presented down:

"When we consider this topic generally, such discrimination was made. The order of candidates I know people who must be in higher order were in low order. However; generally, appropriate order was done." (P1).

"I adduced from my own province, school administrators who were successful in their own school really, accomplished in this exam." (P3).

1e. The Assessment Of The Participants On Whether Anything Was Taken Into Consideration Except For The Candidates' Skills During The Selection Process

Seventeen participants stated that something was taken into consideration during the selection process of school administrators. Thirteen participants mentioned some reasons. It was thought that intimacy with superiors, unions, political authority (8), initiative of evaluators come into prominence (3) and influential contacts became effective in this process. However, two participants believed that nothing was influential in this process rather than skills of candidates. The views of participants who thought that anything was influential rather than skills of participants were given below:

"The person who had close relationships with superiors and unions became successful. Ostensibly, one or two successful administrators were prolonged their duty term." (P5).

"Rather than their skills, world views of candidates were taken into consideration."
(P17).

"Because of partial criterions, the exams depend on initiative of evaluators. The exam didn't evaluate skill." (P2).

"That is, absolutely something was asked for. Since people call and connect with someone to gain a footing. We can't understand how effective it is. But they are people. They call and harass someone by thinking that something could be done." (P16).

2. The views of the school administrator candidates on the application of this regulation were appropriate for career principle were evaluated under eight different aspects. The assessment of the participants on whether

- a) The administrators who were assigned as a result of administrators selection process had qualities requiring being administrators;
- b) The administrators were given an opportunity for building career (having a position and being known in the organization) as a result of administrator selection application;
- c) The administrators were given an opportunity for their promotion as a result of administrator selection application;
- d) The talented administrators were given an opportunity for holding on their organizations as a result of administrator selection application;
- e) The administrators were given an opportunity for working comfortably in their organizations as a result of administrator selection application;
- f) The administrators were given an appropriate fee as a result of administrator selection application;
- g) This application encourages the administrators of becoming an expert;
- h) Age and seniority or knowledge and skill were considered important in the exam process;

2a. The assessment of the participants on whether the administrators who were assigned as a result of administrator selection process had qualities requiring being administrators.

Sixteen participants thought that the administrators who were assigned as a result of administrator selection process hadn't qualities requiring being administrators before their assignments while two participants stated that the new administrators had these qualities. One participant wasn't sure and believed that this topic becoming

definite as time passed. The view of participant who stated that administrators who were assigned as a result of administrator's selection process hadn't qualities requiring being administrators before their assignments were given below:

"I don't think that becoming an expert isn't taken into consideration. The people who had worked as a teacher for three years became administrators. That is, the person who wants to be an administrator should work at specific duties gradually such as military service and police. Then s\he should be an administrator and being an administrator should be a job as well as it should be assessed as an institution. Before working as a teacher for 3 or 5 years, a person shouldn't be a vice principal. A person who has worked for 2-3 years shouldn't be an administrator." (P5).

The view of participant who stated that administrators who were assigned as a result of administrator's selection process had qualities requiring being administrators before their assignments were given below:

"I can say that the people I know now have these qualities" (P4).

The other statements were presented below:

"We don't know anything exactly. We see how many administrators know this job, how many administrators have representative skills when assignments have been completed. Especially, for vice principals, we see how many people can promote." (P2).

"Many people had graduate degree from the universities which unions made an agreement with because master and doctorate are gotten extra point in appendix 1. This gets positive effect. It gives little opportunity for building a career and being an expert." (P3).

2b. The assessment of the participants on whether the administrators were given an opportunity for building career (having a position and being known in the organization) as a result of administrator selection application

Fifteen participants thought that the application of administrator selection didn't provide opportunities for building career, having a location and being known in organization. One participant believed this application could supply this kind of opportunity if a candidate had a well-known person and institution. And the other two participants stated that building career, having a location and being known in

organization depended on the administrators. The views of participants who stated that the application of administrator selection didn't provide opportunities for building career, having a location and being known in organization were given below:

"No, it doesn't give opportunity for career and it hinders us. Moreover, it doesn't provide any location in an organization. Only, it assigns us." (P2).

"No, absolutely, it doesn't give these kind of opportunities. We will be teachers again four or eight years later. There isn't any statement on what the administrator will do after eight years. The administrator will be a teacher again." (P3).

"It doesn't provide these opportunities in this situation. If I experienced a problem with the president of school council, I would have negative points from him\her four years later. The proportion of the points unbalance easily. I believe that this situation harms the working willingness of the administrators." (P12).

The views of participants who thought that building career, having a location and being known in organization depended on the administrators were given below:

"Small details show the successful administrators while they are doing their own work because the regulation covers everybody. These opportunities depend on the working style of the administrators." (P4).

Finally, the view of the participant who believed that this application could supply this kind of opportunity if a candidate had a well-known person.

"Maybe it becomes rarely and randomly but generally, the people who supply their power from well-known people and institutions have priority." (P19).

2c. The assessment of the participants on whether the administrators were given an opportunity for their promotion as a result of administrator selection application.

Fifteen participants stated that this regulation didn't enable the administrators to promote in their career while three participants thought that this opportunity was given only to some administrators. However, one participants believed that the regulation provide promotion of all administrators. The views of participants who thought that this regulation didn't enable the administrators to promote in their career were given below:

“This regulation determines only the administrators of institutions. It doesn’t provide the teachers to promote until they become permanent undersecretary in national education ministry. A teacher can be an administrator of institution for eight years with this regulation. But the next process is close. Such a regulation should be prepared to enable teachers to promote gradually until they become permanent undersecretary in national education ministry only when we could mention career principle.” (P2). “No, it doesn’t provide this kind of opportunity. It only prolongs the duty for four years. If the government changed, the new government would end the duties of present administrators.” (P3).

The views of participants who thought that this regulation provide for the promotion of only some administrators to in their career were given below:

“If you had a friend who worked in superior position and this situation were effective while selecting administrators, your promotion would happen and you would have this opportunity until this situation ends.”(P6).

“Becoming an administrator is a promotion for teachers. Undoubtedly, this regulation gives this opportunity. This job provides them a higher position unavoidably. When we say an administrator, all teachers think that the administrator must understand mathematics to physics.” (P16).

2d. The Assessment of The Participants On Whether The Talented Administrators Were Given An Opportunity For Holding On Their Organizations As A Result Of Administrators Selection Application

Seventeen participants stated that this regulation didn’t provide for the administrators to hold on their organizations. However, two participants thought this regulation enabled administrators for it more or less but application of the regulation didn’t ensure this opportunity. The views of participants who thought that this regulation didn’t provide the administrators to hold on their organizations were given below:

“Unfortunately, we can’t hold the skilled and qualified administrators on their organizations. Private schools can transfer these kinds of administrators by giving them more money and opportunity as well as transferring fee. However, this happens only for three or five from a thousand administrators. There are skilled but infamous

administrators who do their work correctly. They don't have advertisement ability and they can't be recognized." (P2).

"It doesn't provide now because we was assigned for four years and this is a second job. The main job is teaching. I will return to teaching soon. So this regulation doesn't provide the administrators to hold on their organizations. Now they are teachers who were successful administrators in the past. The other successful administrators took good proposals from private schools, municipality and specialized courses. But the specialized courses are going to be closed. So the administrators are being transferred to private schools, municipality. If I were them, I would do so." (P3).

The views of participants who stated that this regulation enabled administrators for it more or less but application of the regulation didn't ensure this opportunity were given below:

"The regulation provides the administrators who have successful career, something for continuing their duty successfully. But the evaluator can't assess objectively so the successful administrators have seemed unsuccessful and unsuccessful administrators have seemed successful." (P5).

"The regulation enables this opportunity on the paper. However; in its application, this opportunity wasn't provided. Unfortunately, I think that the evaluator sent away the administrators who worked properly or prevented the talented candidates from entering the system by being oppressed by various factors." (P18).

2e. The assessment of the participants on whether the administrators were given an opportunity for working comfortably in their organizations as a result of administrator selection application.

Sixteen participants thought that the application of administrator's selection didn't let administrators to work comfortably while three participants believed this application provides appropriate working conditions. The views of participants who stated that this application didn't enable administrators to work without difficulty were given below:

"There aren't any labour security and guarantee. In the other regulations, there were some conditions about being dismissed. We could be dismissed as a result of investigations and negative works through laws and regulations. We haven't been

appointed but we have been assigned. Our duties depend on the decision of the people who assigned us. They have right to dismiss by saying that this administrator is inadequate without presenting any documents. The administrators aren't free because of this. So they can't produce different things with the fear they can be dismissed. Being successful contains several risks. The statements which are that my school haven't got any problem and success isn't important as well as my superiors don't get angry and dismiss me, have started." (P2).

"It is sometimes necessary to make radical decisions and apply them in order that a school administrator can be successful. I think that school administrators who are assigned for four years through the new regulation can't use their initiatives to give better education service. They can make lots of concessions to have better relationship with stakeholders in their schools and their superiors. They can only wait to complete their duty term in order that they seem sweet. Sometimes, the superiors desire something which is inappropriate to the laws or to school processing. Before this regulation, we couldn't accept this but now, we see how the new administrators behave in this situation as time passes." (P7).

The views of participants who stated that this application provides administrators to work comfortably were given below:

"Being an administrator is very stressful work. The only positive side of it is I will work with the district directorate of national education comfortably if s\he select me. Moreover; I will tell my troubles easily and work better and in a solution oriented way rather than causing problems." (P3). "On the other side, the new administrators have little time in their position. I think that they will strive hard. When the administrators were appointed, the aim process was open. Now, it is limited. I agree with the regulation for this side." (P12).

2f. The assessment of the participants on whether the administrators were given an appropriate fee as a result of administrator selection application.

All of the participants stated that the regulation didn't provide appropriate fee by saying some reasons. Some participants thought that the administrators didn't have more money than the teachers in the same school. And some participants said that there weren't any differences between the administrators who worked in the small schools and the administrators working in the big schools. There were some views bellows:

“The appropriate fee isn’t provided because management is seen as a second work. On the thirteenth June, some superiors attempted to give administrators eighteen hours additional courses fee by saying that the administrators were teachers. The administrators have same amount of money as the vice principals isn’t right.” (P4).

“This regulation only explains how the administrators are assigned. Although administrators have lots of responsibility and work for ten or twelve hours in a day, they don’t have much more money than teachers.” (P7).

2g. The Assessment of The Participants on whether This Application Encourages The Administrators of Becoming An Expert

Seventeen participants thought that the regulation didn’t encourage becoming an expert. One participant believed that the regulation didn’t cause to try to become an expert and another participant thought so but application didn’t let it because some negativeness in the application was experienced. The views of participants who thought that the regulation didn’t encourage becoming an expert were given below.

“I don’t think so because the administrators who have already become experts were dismissed. Unfortunately, it was showed that there was no use becoming an expert and it wasn’t important by being kidded with them.” (P13).

“The regulation doesn’t encourage becoming an expert. It was assigned as an administrator. After four years, it won’t be definite. Uncertainty will be created.” (P14).

The view of the participant who thought that the regulation encouraged becoming an expert was given below:

“Actually, the regulation encourages becoming an expert. The people, who are working as administrators, think that they will be at higher position or if they returned to teaching, they wouldn’t make same mistakes. For example, they wouldn’t enter the class late. They would become experts.” (P16).

The view of the participant who thought that the regulation encouraged but the application of it didn’t let to become an expert was given below:

“On the one side, I thought that administrators tried to do all they could to become experts because they were assessed by stakeholders. On the other side, the regulation has open factors with the respect to administrators’ effects on stakeholders. Without becoming

an expert, they can prolong their duty term through human relationships with stakeholders. Because of its wrong application, it might not encourage becoming an expert.” (P18).

2h. The Assessments of the Participants on If Age and Seniority or Knowledge and Skill Were Considered Important in the Exam Process

Ten participants thought neither age and seniority nor knowledge and skills of candidates were taken into consideration. Five participants believed that both age and seniority were given importance. Two participants stated that knowledge and skill were considered important. One participant thought sometimes knowledge and skills sometimes age and seniority were taken into consideration. One participant said that all criteria were considered important. The views of the participants who thought that neither age and seniority nor knowledge and skills of candidates were taken into consideration were given below:

“I think nothing was considered important in this application. In my opinion, knowledge and skill should be taken into consideration. And I emphasized before that career and competency weren’t considered important in the assignments of the administrators.” (P8).

“Neither age and seniority nor knowledge and skills of candidates were considered important. Only the close relationship of candidates with the party in power was taken into consideration.” (P10).

The view of the participant who thought that age and seniority was considered important was given below:

“We can see that age and seniority are considered important now because it is difficult to be evaluated the knowledge and skill. As if they took easy way out but the right application is knowledge and skill should be evaluate through specific criteria. It is selected the easiest way. And giving right to the older administrators show that age and seniority were taken into consideration.” (P1).

The view of the participant who thought sometimes knowledge and skills sometimes age and seniority were taken into consideration was given below:

“Knowledge and skill should be taken into consideration. Age and seniority wouldn’t cause learning if the person wasn’t willing. But the evaluators have initiative in this process. They could select a candidate for the reason that s\he has worked as an administrators for a long time or is young and has a graduate degree as well as becomes an expert. Both of them happened. But it was confused. These weren’t considered as criterions.” (P2).

The view of the participant who stated that knowledge and skill were considered important was given below:

“Age and seniority weren’t taken into consideration. Knowledge and skill were considered more important. It was thought that the new administrators would be more efficient. I give an example; the administrators who are older than me couldn’t pass the exam.” (P3).

The view of the participant who thought that all criterions were considered important was given below:

“The regulation gave points to age and seniority of candidates through appendix 2 form and knowledge was tried to evaluate through the oral exam.” (P7).

4. Discussion and Conclusion

In this study, the views of the school administrator candidates about the regulation imposed by Ministry of National Education (MNE) on selection and assignment an administrator were received to examine this regulation through competence and career principles of human resources.

The views of school administrator candidates on suitability of competency principle for the application of selection and assignment an administrator for formal schools imposed by MNE were in direction that everybody was informed about the selection exam. Their statements about the exam having being announced and everyone’s awareness of it showed that the first necessary step for selection of appropriate sampling from the widest population and the assessment of human resources effectively had occurred. Anderson (1991) stated that the announcement of school administrator’s selection was beneficial for being constructed appropriate candidate pool and selection of the most competent personnels. Most of the candidates reply to the question about whether the most competent personnels were selected

negatively, so this situation showed that the selection based on competency principle couldn't be done. The selections based on competency principles were crucial for efficiency and effectiveness of organization. In Özdemir's (2013) study it was seen that the teachers and the administrators made an effort for their institution and assisted the organization to achieve their aims when they believed that they were competent and in a fair work environment.

School administrator candidates proposed two main reasons. One of them was the reasons arising from formal procedures. They stated the inadequate selection criteria in the regulation, the inappropriate point distribution, lack of a criteria on administrator experience and objective criteria in the regulation. The other was the reasons arising from the application of the exam. In this respect they mentioned the elimination of successful administrators, suspicion and hesitation on the points given by authorities, being given importance to the political ideas and relationship and short time for the exam. These findings showed that the implementer of the exam behaved partially and subjectively rather than objectively and there were faults arising from the implementers, so this indicated that administrative science and its principles weren't taken into consideration for the school administrator selection in Turkey. Among the reasons of this situation, school administration isn't seen as a professional and scientific job by superior administrators in Turkey could be proposed.

Only one candidate stated a positive view on the criteria required for being an administrator while most of candidates expressed negative views. Some candidates said that criteria didn't include necessary qualities for being an administrator; the discrete condition wanted in the exam, every teacher could become an administrator directly. Most of the candidates thought that participants weren't put into the appropriate order for this job. However; one of the competency principle elements was that the participants could be put into the appropriate order as a result of the exam (Tortop, 1999). Because effective implementations conducted in the appointment process of new personnel will provide equality between the candidates, contribute to the improvement of the organization and affect the work of employees and their decision to stay there (Searle, 2009).

Most of the candidates stated that something was taken into consideration except for the participants' skills during the selection process and among them, intimacy with superiors, unions, political authority as well as initiative of evaluators, influential contacts could be said while skills and leadership style of the participants should be evaluated during the selection of the most competent personnels (Anderson, 1991). When the results of this study were taken into consideration, the application of selection and assignment of formal school administrators, which still has continued in

Turkey and was conducted by MoNE didn't look accordance with competency principle. One of the most important obstacles on conducting the competency principle was that intimacy with political authority and unions having its effect was seen as the prevailing way for being an administrator by the participants who looked for intimacy (some participants said that looking for intimacy was normal. for example 8b). The school administrators are seen as a controller of the education by the government and this causes a problem of a subjective process about assigning and training an administrator (Arslanargun, 2012). However, what is expected to do is to determine the required skill, knowledge and abilities and implement these into the election process and provide a fair and objective election while selecting the school administrators (Schmitt and Schehtman, 1990).

Fairness on hiring decisions is one of the crucial topics for career development area (Wooten & Cobb, 1999). The views of the candidates on the suitability of application of selection and assignment of formal school administrators, conducted by MoNE for career principle were given as follows: most of the candidates stated that administrators assigned as a result of this application hadn't necessary qualities and expertness for being an administrator. According to career principle of human resources management, the personnel who have appropriate education and skills for a specific area in the organization should be provided for short, medium and long term (Martin, 2010). For building a career, personnel shouldn't have little knowledge and skill from every job but being an expert and having deep knowledge on a specific area were necessary. In other words, building a career is possible with qualified personnel that is, skilled labour in modern era (Tortop, 1999). The career principle gives opportunity to the qualified personnel for building a career, holding on and becoming known in their organization. According to the result of this study, most of the candidates stated that this regulation didn't give opportunity to them. The other result of this study was in direction that most of the candidates stated that this regulation didn't give opportunity for promotion in the job. The most important was temporary assignment which is valid for 4 years and every administrator could return to teaching as a result of this regulation. This application results from the idea which being an administrator wasn't accepted as a professional job and the understanding placed in the law as "Teaching is fundamental in the job." The other result of the study was that most of the candidates didn't think that this application enabled competent personnels to hold on their organizations. The competent personnel take machine responsibility for achieving organizational goals and performance increase. If the competent personnels didn't hold on their organizations or were transformed another organization, it would result from the decrease of the standard group performance and Hawthorne researches

showed that the group performance affected the personnel's performances (Aydın, 2010). Lots of researches showed that job satisfaction of competent personnel who didn't think they received compensation for their work would reduce over time and as a result they could leave from their organization (Davis, 1988). According to career principle, Shalley, Gilson and Blum (2000) stated that suitable environment conditions affected creativity of personnels positively so it is necessary that the suitable environment opportunity should be provided but most of the candidates asserted that suitable working environment and appropriate payment weren't make available to the administrators in this regulation. Moreover, they emphasized that lack of these opportunities affected the job satisfaction and pleasure of the personnels negatively at the same time. This situation result in falling off the number of prospect personnels. The appropriate payment in accordance with the job responsibility and additional opportunities with regard to school conditions should be given (Whitaker, 2003). It is important that there is appropriate payment system in the organizations to increase the motivation, job satisfaction and morale of the personnel. Becoming an expert was encouraged in the organization as to career principle (Tortop, 1999). But the research indicated that most of candidates thought becoming an expert wasn't stimulated. Many candidates also stated that neither age and seniority nor knowledge and skill were taken into consideration. Moreover, the number of the candidates who said that age and seniority was considered more important was two times more than the number of the candidates who said that knowledge and skill were considered more important. However, it was stated in another study that the selection of the administrators which was done according to only age and seniority criteria was wrong (Recepoğlu & Kılınc, 2014). However; education and experiences or skills on related job should be taken into consideration and these properties should be used while the candidates are being put in order during interview process (Institute for career research, 2005).

The application of selection and assignment of formal school administrators, conducted by MoNE for career principle wasn't accordance with career principle when the results of this study were examined. While this principle was conducted in the regulation published in 1999 (Kayıkçı, 2001), it hasn't been conducted now during selection of the administrators shows that the principles of the contemporary educational administration have been drifted away. As a result of competency and career principles as well as the ignorance of having a graduate degree weren't given importance, that administrators were selected arbitrarily as Balcı (2008) said, the number of students in the departments which administration and leadership was taught, decreases and these departments hardly were closed owing to scarcity of students. (Kayıkçı & Ercan, 2013).

To sum up, the department whose name was personnel management in Central Organization Diagram in Turkey before, renamed human resource management but the application of school administrator selection is deprived of competency and career which are principles of human resource management. In other words, this application isn't appropriate for competency and career principles. As educational administration hasn't been accepted as a scientific and professional job in Turkey yet, the principles of administration science can't be applied and a school administrator can't be selected in accordance with competency, for which administration science having the 100- year history in Europe and America, requires a necessity. Selection of the public school administrators which is one part of public administration should be done in accordance with human resource management principles based on managerial understanding, appropriate for our age rather than patrimonial bureaucracy of Weber.

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Appendix

Table 1: The Assessment of Participants on Whether the Regulation and Its Application were in Accordance with Competency Principle

	√	-	other
1. Selection of the most competent people	1	18	-
2. The Appropriate Order of Candidates	4	14	1
3. Accessibility to Exam	18	1	-
4. The advantages or disadvantages for participants	14	2	3
5. Being considered Another property rather than competency	17	2	-
6. The realistic conditions for selection of administrators	-	18	1

Table 2: The reasons why the most competent people weren't selected

A. The Reasons Arising From The Regulation	f
The inadequacy of criterions in the regulation	1
The inappropriate distribution of points in the regulation	1
The lack of condition related to have worked as an administrators before	2
The partial criterions of the regulation	2
B. The Reason Resulting From Its Application	
The elimination of the successful principals	3
Providing advantages for the people who were good at memorizing and lucky	1
Hesitation and suspicion for the points given in the exam.	2
The opinion on selected people weren't leaders.	1
The opinion on political views were at the forefront	3
Being allocated short time for the exam	2

Table 3: What Kind Of Properties Were Taken Into Consideration Rather Than Skills of Candidates during the Selection Process of School Administrators to Participants

	f
Intimacy with superiors, unions, political authority was asked for.	8
Initiative of evaluators come into prominence	3
Influential contacts happened	2
Something was asked for	4
Nothing was asked for	2

Table 4: The Assessment of Participants on Whether the Regulation and Its Application were in Accordance with Career Principle

	√	-	other
1. Having required qualities	2	16	1
2. Being given an opportunity for building career	1	15	3
3. Being given an opportunity for their promotion	3	15	1
4. Being given an opportunity for holding on their organizations	2	17	-

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5. Being given an opportunity for working comfortably	3	16	-
6. Being given an appropriate payment	-	19	-
7. Being encouraged becoming an expert	1	17	1
8. Age and Seniority or Knowledge and Skill Were Considered Important	9	10	-

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